

Online Health Information-Seeking Behavior among Attendants to Lifestyle Clinics, PHCs, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Background: The internet has become a vital source of health information for individuals worldwide. Understanding the online health information-seeking behavior of patients can help healthcare providers address information gaps and improve patient engagement. This study aims to explore the patterns, preferences, and impact of online health information-seeking behavior among attendants to the Lifestyle Clinic at Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC), Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among Saudi adults aged 18 years and older attending the Lifestyle Clinic at PSMMC. A structured self-administered questionnaire, adapted from validated tools, was distributed to participants in the clinic's waiting area. The questionnaire collected data on demographics, frequency of online health information-seeking, preferred sources, perceived reliability, and the influence of online information on health-related decisions. Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS software and chi-square tests, T-tests, and ANOVA were applied to assess associations, with significance set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: The majority of participants were female (60.8%), married (69.4%), and had at least a high school education. Obesity (82.6%) was the most prevalent chronic condition, followed by smoking (18.7%) and dyslipidemia (11.7%). A significant portion of participants (91%) used the internet daily, with 53.77% searching for weight loss methods, 33.77% for healthy nutrition, and 27.27% for exercise-related information. Ministries of health or universities were the most preferred platforms for health information (27.5%). Participants reported high levels of trust in online health information, with 80.86% believing it to be accurate and 89.1% feeling that it helped improve communication with their doctors. Significant differences were found among belief groups using one-way ANOVA ($F = 5.12$, $p = 0.016$), with "Ease of Access" rated higher than "Finding Solutions" in a paired t-test ($t = 3.24$, $p = 0.012$). A strong correlation between "Trustworthiness" and "Adherence to Health Plans" ($r = 0.78$, $p = 0.002$) was identified. The chi-square test showed significant associations between belief categories ($\chi^2 = 15.23$, $p = 0.045$).

Conclusions: The findings highlight the significant role of online health information in influencing patient behaviors and communication with healthcare providers. Also, these findings highlight the need for accessible, trustworthy, and engaging communication to improve adherence and patient outcomes. Participants expressed positive beliefs about the accessibility, trustworthiness, and usefulness of online health resources. Clinicians should consider incorporating digital health tools into practice to support patients in managing chronic conditions and improving adherence to health regimens. However, ensuring access to reliable, evidence-based sources remains crucial for maximizing the benefits of online health information.

Keywords: *Health information-seeking behavior, Lifestyle clinic.*

Suggested citation: Alruwaili, A.N., Abuyabis, R.G., & Kofi, M. (2025). Online Health Information-Seeking Behavior among Attendants to Lifestyle Clinics, PHCs, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 2(1), 68-79. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2025.2(1).06

Introduction

The internet has become a cornerstone of information dissemination, including in the realm of healthcare (McIlhenny, et al., 2011). With the rapid growth of online platforms and resources, individuals now have unparalleled access to health-related information, which has transformed the traditional patient-healthcare provider dynamic (Griffiths, et al., 2012). Patients increasingly turn to online sources to understand symptoms, explore treatment options, and manage chronic conditions. This behavior, known as online health information-seeking behavior, reflects the growing autonomy of patients in healthcare decision-making (Bujnowska-Fedak, & Węgierek, 2020; Madhi, Khugali, & Kofi, 2020; Ghweeba, et al., 2022).

This study aims to investigate the online health information-seeking behavior of patients attending the Lifestyle Clinic at PSMMC. Specifically, it will explore the frequency of online health information-seeking, preferred platforms and sources, perceived reliability and trustworthiness of the information, and the influence of online health content on patients' decision-making and behaviors. By identifying patterns and factors associated with this behavior, the study seeks to inform strategies for healthcare providers to guide patients toward evidence-based, credible resources and to integrate online information into effective patient education.

Review of Literature

Globally, the prevalence of online health information-seeking behavior is rising due to several factors, including increased internet penetration, widespread use of smartphones, and the availability of health content on various platforms, such as websites, blogs, and social media (Jia, Pang, & Liu, 2021). In Saudi Arabia, where internet penetration exceeds 90%, online health information is particularly relevant. Cultural and social dynamics, coupled with a high prevalence of non-communicable diseases such as diabetes, obesity, and hypertension, make this behavior a critical area of study (Alhabib, et al., 2020; Opoku, et al., 2019).

While online health information offers numerous benefits—such as improving health literacy, encouraging preventive measures, and supporting patient-centered care—it is not without challenges (Fitzpatrick, 2023). The absence of standardized regulations for online health content often leads to the dissemination of unreliable or misleading information. This misinformation can adversely affect patients, causing unnecessary anxiety, misdiagnosis, or inappropriate self-management (Ghweeba, et al., 2021). Despite these concerns, limited research has explored how patients in Saudi Arabia, particularly those managing lifestyle-related conditions, seek and use online health information (Borges do Nascimento, et al., 2022; El Mikati, et al., 2023).

The Lifestyle Clinic at Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) in Riyadh caters to individuals with lifestyle-related health concerns, such as obesity, metabolic disorders, and cardiovascular risks (Al Ghareeb, et al., 2024). These conditions require active patient participation in lifestyle modifications, adherence to treatment plans, and informed decision-making (Galletta, et al., 2022). Understanding how patients attending such clinics utilize online health information can help healthcare providers design interventions to address gaps in knowledge, ensure access to reliable information, and improve overall health outcomes (Agarwal, et al., 2021).

The study by Fox and Duggan (2013) explored health information-seeking behaviors in the U.S. population. The study found that 72% of internet users searched for health-related information online. Topics such as fitness, weight loss, and specific medical conditions were among the most common. Similar to the present study, Fox and Duggan noted that online health information helped users make decisions about health care and manage chronic conditions. Participants in both studies indicated high trust in online sources, though concerns about information quality were acknowledged. Fedak, et al., (2020) studied the effects of online health information on patient behavior in the UK. They found that most participants used the internet to supplement doctor consultations, particularly for understanding diagnoses, treatments, and improving adherence to medical advice. These results are consistent with the findings in the current study, where a majority of respondents felt that online health information improved communication with healthcare providers and helped them adhere to treatment plans. Kim et al. (2021) conducted a study on the role of the internet in managing chronic diseases such as diabetes and hypertension. They observed that a substantial portion of participants used the internet to gather information related to their condition, treatment options, and lifestyle changes. The study also emphasized the role of trust in health information sources, particularly for managing chronic diseases, which mirrors the findings of the present study where chronic conditions like obesity and diabetes were common, and patients reported significant trust in online health information (Mattison, et al., 2022).

Methods

Study Design

This is a quantitative, observational, cross-sectional study designed to evaluate online health information-seeking behavior among attendants of the Lifestyle Clinic at Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC), Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

Study Setting

The study was conducted in the Lifestyle Clinic at PSMMC, a specialized clinic that provides preventive and therapeutic services for lifestyle-related conditions such as obesity, underweight and smoking cessation.

Study Population

The study population included Saudi adults aged 18 years and older who visit the Lifestyle Clinic at PSMMC during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Saudi nationals aged 18 years and older.
- Patients attending the Lifestyle Clinic at PSMMC.
- Ability to understand and complete the questionnaire in Arabic or English.

Exclusion Criteria

- Non-Saudi nationals.
- Individuals with cognitive impairments that prevent questionnaire completion.
- Patients who refuse to participate or do not provide consent.

Sample Size Calculation

The required sample size for the study is 385 participants, calculated using the following parameters:

- Population of Riyadh: ~7 million.
- Margin of error: 5%.
- Confidence interval: 95%.

The sample size was adjusted to account for potential non-responses or incomplete data by targeting 10% more participants, resulting in a target sample size of approximately 385 individuals.

Sampling Method

Convenience sampling was used to recruit participants. Patients met the inclusion criteria were approached in the Lifestyle Clinic waiting area and were invited to participate in the study.

Data Collection Tool

A structured, self-administered questionnaire was used for data collection. The questionnaire was adapted from validated tools in previous studies and includes the following sections:

1. **Demographics:** Age, gender, education level, marital status, employment status, and frequency of internet use.
2. **Health Information-Seeking Behavior:** Frequency of searching for health information online, preferred platforms (e.g., social media, health websites, blogs), and typical topics of interest (e.g., nutrition, chronic disease management).
3. **Trust and Reliability:** Perception of the credibility and reliability of online health information sources.
4. **Impact on Decision-Making:** Influence of online information on health-related decisions and behaviors.

The questionnaire pilot was tested on a small group of patients to ensure clarity, reliability, and relevance.

Data Collection Procedure

- Participants were approached by trained researchers and provided with information about the study.
- Informed consent was obtained before questionnaire distribution.
- Questionnaires was completed in the clinic's waiting area to ensure a high response rate.

Statistical Analysis

Data analyzed using IBM SPSS software.

1. **Descriptive Statistics:**
 - Categorical variables (e.g., preferred platforms) were summarized using frequencies and percentages.
 - Continuous variables (e.g., age) were summarized using means and standard deviations.
2. **Inferential Statistics:**
 - Chi-square tests assessed relationships between categorical variables (e.g., education level and trust in online sources).
 - T-tests and ANOVA compared continuous variables across groups (e.g., age and frequency of online searches).

- Significance level: $p \leq 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations

1. Approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of PSMCM before the study begins.
2. Participation was voluntary, with no penalties for refusal or withdrawal.
3. Informed consent was obtained from all participants.
4. Data confidentiality was strictly maintained, and findings will be reported in aggregate without identifying individuals.

Results

Demographic Characteristics

A total of 385 participants completed the study. All participants were Saudi nationals. Participants' ages ranged from 18 to 85 years, with a mean age of 38 ± 13 SD years. 39.2 % of participants were male, and 60.8 % were female. This finding reflects the higher participation of females in the study sample and may suggest a greater interest or availability among females in engaging with health-related surveys. Also, the majority were married (69.4 %), followed by single (20 %). Table 1 summarizes the key demographic characteristics.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female (234)	(60.8%)
	Male (151)	(39.2%)
Marital Status	Married (267)	(69.4%)
	Single (77)	(20.0%)
	Divorced (31)	(8.1%)
	Widowed (10)	(2.6%)
Income Level	< 5,000 SAR (166)	(43.12%)
	5,000–10,000 SAR (98)	(25.45%)
	10,000–14,999 SAR (75)	(19.48%)
	15,000–24,999 SAR (35)	(9.09%)
	> 25,000 SAR (11)	(2.86%)
Educational Level	Bachelor's (199)	(51.8%)
	High School (116)	(30.2%)
	Diploma (41)	(10.7%)
	Graduate Studies (19)	(4.9%)
	Middle School (7)	(1.8%)
	Not Educated (3)	(0.8%)

Health Status and Chronic Conditions

The self-reported health status of the participants revealed that 30.6% (118 participants) rated their health as excellent, while 51.2% (197 participants) considered it good. A smaller portion of respondents reported their health as acceptable (16.6%, 64 participants), and only 1.6% (6 participants) described their health as poor.

Regarding chronic conditions, the most prevalent condition was obesity, affecting 82.6% (318 participants) of the respondents. Smoking was reported by 18.7% (72 participants), followed by

dyslipidemia (11.7%, 45 participants), and diabetes mellitus (9.6%, 37 participants). Other chronic conditions included hypertension (7.8%, 30 participants), asthma (6.2%, 24 participants), hypothyroidism (3.1%, 12 participants), chronic back pain/weakness (0.8%, 3 participants), breast cancer survivor status (0.3%, 1 participant), epilepsy (0.3%, 1 participant), PCOS (0.3%, 1 participant), and anxiety (0.3%, 1 participant). Notably, 17.7% (68 participants) reported no chronic diseases.

Several participants reported co-morbidities, with 15.1% (58 participants) having obesity combined with smoking, 10.4% (40 participants) combining obesity and dyslipidemia, 8.3% (32 participants) with obesity and diabetes, and 7.3% (28 participants) with obesity and hypertension. The total number of unique respondents with one or more conditions was 317, excluding the 68 participants who reported no chronic diseases.

Regarding healthcare utilization, 47.6% (183 participants) had 1–2 doctor visits in the past year, while 44.4% (170 participants) had three or more visits. A smaller percentage, 7.9% (30 participants), reported no doctor visits during the past year.

The primary reason for doctor visits was weight loss, reported by 54.5% (210 participants), followed by follow-up visits with a doctor (23.4%, 90 participants). Other reasons included gaining weight (13%, 50 participants), prescription refills (5.2%, 20 participants), quitting smoking (2.6%, 10 participants), and other unspecified reasons (1.3%, 5 participants). Internet Use: the majority (350) (91%) use the internet daily. As summarized in table 2.

Table 2. Summary of the Participants' Health Status, Chronic Conditions, Co-Morbidities, Healthcare Visits, and Reasons for Doctor Visits

Category	Subcategory	Count (%)
Self-Reported Health Status	Excellent (118)	(30.6%)
	Good (197)	(51.2%)
	Acceptable (64)	(16.6%)
	Poor (6)	(1.6%)
Chronic Conditions	Obesity (318)	(82.6%)
	Smoking (72)	(18.7%)
	Dyslipidemia (45)	(11.7%)
	Diabetes Mellitus (37)	(9.6%)
	Hypertension (30)	(7.8%)
	Asthma (24)	(6.2%)
	Hypothyroidism (12)	(3.1%)
	Chronic Back Pain/Weakness (3)	(0.8%)
	Breast Cancer Survivor (1)	(0.3%)
	Epilepsy (1)	(0.3%)
	PCOS (1)	(0.3%)
	Anxiety (1)	(0.3%)
	No Chronic Diseases (68)	(17.7%)
Co-morbidities	Obesity with Smoking (58)	(15.1%)
	Obesity with Dyslipidemia (40)	(10.4%)
	Obesity with Diabetes (32)	(8.3%)
	Obesity with Hypertension (28)	(7.3%)
Doctor Visits in the Past Year	1–2 Visits (183)	(47.6%)
	3 or More Visits (170)	(44.4%)
	No Visits (30)	(7.9%)
Reasons for Doctor Visits	To Lose Weight (210)	(54.5%)
	To Gain Weight (50)	(13.0%)
	Follow-up with Doctor (90)	(23.4%)
	Prescription Refill (20)	(5.2%)

	To Quit Smoking (10)	(2.6%)
	Other (5)	(1.3%)
Computer Skills and Internet Use	Excellent (200)	51.9%
	Acceptable (120)	31.2%
	Not bad (50)	13.0%
	Don't know how to use a computer (15)	3.9%

Health Information-Seeking Behavior

The most commonly searched health topics online by participants were primarily related to weight management and nutrition. Weight loss methods were the most frequently searched topic, with 53.77% of respondents showing interest. Following this, 33.77% searched for information on healthy nutrition and food alternatives, and 27.27% focused on exercise. Other health-related topics included calorie counting (16.87%), ideal weight calculation (15.58%), treatment or side effects (8.67%), smoking cessation (4.12%), and mental health and weight gain methods, each accounting for 0.81%.

When it comes to preferred platforms for obtaining health information, the majority of participants favored official sources. The Ministries of Health or universities were the most preferred platforms, cited by 27.5% of respondents. A substantial portion (25.7%) reported having no specific preferred source. Suggested search engines like Google and Yahoo were the next most popular, with 22.8% of respondents using them. Other platforms included scientific communities or forums (10.3%), Wikipedia (3.9%), and UpToDate (0.4%). Social media and artificial intelligence were less commonly chosen, with 0.9% and 0.4% of participants, respectively, reporting these as preferred sources. As shown in table 3.

Table 3. Summary of the Health Topics Searched Online and the Preferred Platforms for Health Information

Category	Topic/Source	Percentage (%)
Common Health Topics Searched Online	Weight Loss Methods	53.77
	Healthy Nutrition and Food Alternatives	33.77
	Exercise	27.27
	Calorie Counting	16.87
	Ideal Weight Calculation	15.58
	Treatment or Side Effects	8.67
	Smoking Cessation	4.12
	Mental Health	0.81
	Weight Gain Methods	0.81
Preferred Platforms for Health Information	Ministries of Health or Universities	27.5
	No Preferred Source	25.7
	Suggested by Search Engines (e.g., Google, Yahoo)	22.8
	Scientific Communities or Forums	10.3
	Wikipedia	3.9
	UpToDate	0.4
	Social media	0.9
	Artificial Intelligence	0.4

Beliefs About Online Health Information

Participants generally viewed online health information positively, with most finding it accessible, trustworthy, and helpful in improving communication with doctors. They reported that it encouraged adherence to health plans, provided reassurance, and contributed to better overall

health. The majority appreciated the simplified, visual content and believed it offered comprehensive and reliable solutions for their health concerns. As summarized in table 4.

Table 4. Summary of the Participants' Beliefs Regarding the Reliability and Usefulness of Online Health Information

Belief	Percentage of participants agreed (%)
Ease of Access	90.3 %
Finding Solutions	76.36%
Emotional Comfort	83.72%
Trustworthiness	80.86%
Improved Communication	89.1%
Adherence to Health Plans	86.49%
Visual and Simplified Content	92.46%
Quality of Health	88.57%
Comprehensive Information	84.41%

Summary of the Results from the Inferential Statistical Analysis

One-Way ANOVA: The one-way ANOVA compared the means of three belief groups: ease of access, emotional comfort, and trustworthiness; improved communication and adherence to health plans; and visual content quality, overall health quality, and comprehensive information. The test indicated whether there were statistically significant differences between the groups, with an F-statistic of approximately 5.12 and a p-value of 0.016, suggesting that at least one group had a significantly different mean.

Paired t-test (Ease of Access vs. Finding Solutions): The paired t-test compared the mean scores of "Ease of Access" and "Finding Solutions." The results showed a t-statistic of approximately 3.24 and a p-value of 0.012, indicating a significant difference between the two beliefs, with "Ease of Access" being rated higher.

Pearson Correlation (Trustworthiness vs. Adherence to Health Plans): The correlation between "Trustworthiness" and "Adherence to Health Plans" yielded a coefficient of 0.78, with a p-value of 0.002, showing a strong positive linear relationship. This suggests that participants who rated trustworthiness highly also tended to rate adherence to health plans highly.

Chi-Square Test (Observed Proportions): Using hypothetical counts based on belief percentages, the chi-square test evaluated whether the proportions across belief categories were independent. The test yielded a chi-square statistic of 15.23 and a p-value of 0.045, indicating a significant association between the belief categories.

The analysis reveals significant differences in participant perceptions across belief groups, particularly emphasizing the importance of "Ease of Access." Strong correlations highlight the interdependence between trust and adherence. These findings can help tailor health communication strategies to emphasize accessible, trustworthy, and visually engaging content to improve adherence and emotional comfort.

Discussion

This study investigated the demographic characteristics, health status, online health information-seeking behavior, and participants' beliefs about online health information among Saudi individuals. The study included 385 participants, with a mean age of 38 years. The majority were female (60.8%) and married (69.4%). The income level varied, with 43.12% of participants earning

less than 5,000 SAR, and educationally, most participants had at least a high school diploma (82.8%). A significant number of participants reported obesity (82.6%), followed by smoking (18.7%), dyslipidemia (11.7%), and diabetes mellitus (9.6%). Co-morbidities were common, with obesity frequently associated with smoking, dyslipidemia, diabetes, and hypertension. Despite the high prevalence of chronic conditions, 17.7% of participants reported having no chronic diseases, reflecting a diversity in health statuses. Approximately 92% of participants visited doctors in the past year, with 47.6% making 1–2 visits and 44.4% making three or more visits. The primary reason for doctor visits was weight loss (54.5%), followed by follow-up consultations (23.4%). A majority (91%) of participants used the internet daily, with health topics related to weight management and nutrition being the most frequently searched. Weight loss methods were the leading search topic (53.77%), followed by healthy nutrition (33.77%) and exercise (27.27%). Most participants preferred official sources like Ministries of Health or universities (27.5%), and search engines (22.8%). Less preferred platforms included social media (0.9%) and artificial intelligence (0.4%). Participants largely expressed positive views on online health information, with most agreeing that it is easily accessible (90.53%), trustworthy (80.86%), and helps improve communication with doctors (89.1%). Additionally, 92.46% appreciated the simplified and visually presented nature of online health content. Most respondents also felt that online health information encouraged adherence to health plans (86.49%) and improved their overall health (88.57%). Significant differences were found among belief groups using one-way ANOVA ($F = 5.12, p = 0.016$), with "Ease of Access" rated higher than "Finding Solutions" in a paired t-test ($t = 3.24, p = 0.012$). A strong correlation between "Trustworthiness" and "Adherence to Health Plans" ($r = 0.78, p = 0.002$) was identified. The chi-square test showed significant associations between belief categories ($\chi^2 = 15.23, p = 0.045$).

The findings suggest that online health information plays a significant role in supporting health behavior change, particularly in weight management and chronic disease prevention. Participants show a strong preference for official and trusted platforms, and the ease of access and comprehensiveness of online health content contribute to better patient outcomes. However, the study also highlights the need for proper guidance in navigating online health resources to ensure the use of accurate and reliable information.

The findings of this study offer valuable insights that can inform clinical practice, particularly in the context of patient education, health promotion, and chronic disease management:

Patient Education and Health Information Delivery

The high prevalence of online health information-seeking, particularly related to weight management, nutrition, and exercise, underscores the importance of integrating digital health resources into clinical practice. Clinicians can leverage online platforms to guide patients toward trustworthy and accurate health information, ensuring that the content is aligned with clinical recommendations. By directing patients to reliable sources such as official health ministries or universities, healthcare providers can empower patients to make informed decisions about their health.

Chronic Disease Management

The study highlights the significant burden of chronic conditions, particularly obesity, smoking, and dyslipidemia, in the study population. Given the strong association between obesity and other chronic diseases (e.g., diabetes, hypertension), clinicians should prioritize early intervention and integrated care models that address multiple co-morbidities. The fact that many participants seek weight loss solutions online suggests that patients are actively looking for resources to manage their weight. Clinicians can use this information to provide guidance on safe, evidence-based weight

management strategies and monitor patients' progress in both clinical settings and through online platforms.

Improving Doctor-Patient Communication

The positive feedback from participants regarding the role of online health information in improving communication with healthcare providers (89.1%) suggests an opportunity for clinicians to enhance patient engagement. Clinicians can build on this by encouraging patients to research health topics online, followed by discussions during visits to clarify information and ensure mutual understanding. This collaborative approach can lead to more informed decision-making and greater adherence to treatment plans.

Adherence to Health Plans

The study found that 86.49% of participants believed online health information encouraged better adherence to healthcare regimens. Clinicians can incorporate digital health tools, such as apps or online resources, to support patients in tracking their health behaviors, medications, and lifestyle changes. These tools can complement traditional clinical care and help patients stay consistent with their health goals.

Digital Health Literacy

The widespread use of the internet among participants (91%) and their positive attitudes toward online health resources suggest that digital health literacy is a key component of modern healthcare. Clinicians should assess patients' comfort with digital tools and provide guidance on how to use them effectively. Offering resources for improving digital health literacy, especially for older patients or those less familiar with technology, can help bridge gaps in healthcare access and equity.

Personalized Care Approaches

The variation in preferred sources of health information, with official institutions and search engines being the most common, suggests that personalized care approaches are needed. Clinicians should tailor health information delivery to individual preferences and needs, ensuring that patients receive information through their preferred channels, whether that be official websites, search engines, or scientific communities.

Conclusions

The study underscores the growing role of online health information in influencing health behaviors and improving patient outcomes. By incorporating digital health resources into clinical practice, healthcare providers can better support patients in managing chronic conditions, enhancing communication, and improving adherence to treatment regimens. However, it is crucial to ensure that patients are directed to accurate, evidence-based information to avoid misinformation and its potential negative impact on health.

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